

CO-INJECTION RESIN TRANSFER MOLDING OF CARBON/EPOXY - FOAM - CARBON/PHENOLIC MULTILAYER INTEGRAL COMPOSITES

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1 General Introduction

The primary requirements for a hypersonic aircraft structure are low density, high mechanical performance, thermal protection and heat insulation, respectively. Traditionally, the composite structure applied in the hypersonic aircraft was manufactured with the step by step method and then jointing them with glue. It not only makes the manufacturing process more difficulty and complication and more fabrication cost, but also less reliability of the whole structure. A new load bearing/heat insulation/thermal protection integral composite structure which is manufactured by the Co-injection RTM (CIRTM)[1-3] is developed, the load bearing layer materials are carbon fiber reinforced epoxy (carbon/epoxy) composites, the heat insulation layer materials are low density and low thermal conductivity materials such as foams or silica aerogel materials, the thermal protection layer or ablation layer materials are carbon/phenolic composites.

In this paper, the CIRTM process is described and used to fabricate carbon/epoxy - foam - carbon/phenolic multilayer integral composites. The primary CIRTM process parameters are investigated, and the optimal process parameters are determined according to the inner structure. The interface microstructure and the interlaminar shear strength of the specimen fabricated by CIRTM are studied compared to those of multilayer composites manufactured by fabricating the layers separately and subsequently bonding them together.

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials

Carbon fiber cloth obtain from Toray Ind. Inc. is primary reinforcement. The epoxy resin system consist of E-44 epoxy resin and agent GA327, which obtained from Yueyang Epoxy Co. and Yixing Jiangnan medical refine factory respectively, are used as matrix of load bearing layer. PMI foam ROHACELL[®] XT 110 obtained from Degussa

Corporation, Germany is used as heat insulation layer material. Benzoxazine, a kind of novel phenolic resin, obtained from Sichuan University, is used as the matrix of thermal protection layer.

2.2 Manufacturing procedure

Fig.1 shows the experimental setup used, including a detail of the lay-up. The designed thickness of load bearing layer, heat insulation layer and thermal protection layer are 3mm, 10mm, 3mm respectively. PMI foam can serve as separating layer and keeping the two resins completely separate. The integral composite specimen are fabricated by the variety of process conditions such as vacuum assisted, fiber volume fraction, injection pressure and injection temperature. The inner structure manufactured by different process parameters are studied, therefore, the optimal process parameters are determined.

2.3 Interlaminar shear test

The specimen sketch for interlaminar shear test is shown as Fig.2, the dimension values are as follows, $H=45\text{mm}$, $B=50\text{mm}$, $h=30\text{mm}$, $b=2\text{mm}$, which h is the length and b the width of the interface tested. An interlaminar shear device, shown as Fig.3, is used to load a specimen such that the entire load would be supported by the interface between the two layers. The test method is referred to Monnard et al. paper[4]. Once the actual load P is known, the shear stress, τ , is calculated based on

$$\tau = \frac{P}{bh} \quad (1)$$

3 Results and Conclusions

3.1 Process parameters optimization

Vacuum assisted

Keeping the fiber perform fraction of carbon/epoxy layer and carbon/phenolic layer both at the level of 45.6%, injection pressure at 0.1MPa, injection temperature at 80°C, the PMI foam core sandwich composite specimen are manufactured with vacuum assisted and without vacuum assisted respectively,

and the section photos are shown as Fig.4. It can be seen that the thickness of carbon/epoxy layer and carbon/phenolic layer are both 3mm, which accord with the designed. Moreover, the PMI foam isn't infiltrated by the epoxy resin and phenolic resin.

The SEM photos of the specimen fabricated with and without vacuum assisted are shown as Fig.5 and Fig.6. The porosities of carbon/epoxy layer and carbon/phenolic layer reduce much with vacuum assisted compared to without vacuum assisted, therefore, vacuum assisted is indispensable to fabricate excellent integral composites.

Fiber fraction

Keeping injection pressure at 0.1MPa, injection temperature at 80°C, with vacuum assisted, the PMI foam core sandwich composite specimen are manufactured with fiber fraction of 38% and 53.2%, and the section photos are shown as Fig.7. It can be seen that the PMI foam isn't infiltrated by the epoxy resin and phenolic resin, but the thicknesses of carbon/epoxy layer and carbon/phenolic layer of the specimen increase from 3mm to 3.2mm with fiber fraction improved from 45.6% to 53.2%, so the proper fiber fraction for manufacturing integral composites is 45.6%.

Injection pressure

Keeping the fiber fraction at 45.6%, injection temperature at 80°C, with vacuum assisted, the PMI foam core sandwich composite specimen are manufactured with injection pressure increased to 0.3MPa, and the section photos are shown as Fig.8. It can be seen that the PMI foam isn't infiltrated by the epoxy resin and phenolic resin, and the thicknesses of carbon/epoxy layer and carbon/phenolic layer of the specimen accord with the designed. Compared to the section photo of the specimen fabricated with the injection pressure of 0.1MPa(Fig.4 b), the conclusion can be given that the variety of injection pressure has little impact on the thickness of integral composites.

Injection temperature

Keeping the fiber fraction at 45.6%, injection pressure at 0.1MPa, with vacuum assisted, the PMI foam core sandwich composite specimen is manufactured with injection temperature increased to 90°C, and the section photos are shown as Fig.9. It can be seen that the PMI foam isn't infiltrated by the epoxy resin and phenolic resin, and the thicknesses of carbon/epoxy layer and carbon/phenolic layer of the specimen accord with

the designed. Compared to the section photo of the specimen fabricated with the injection temperature of 80°C(Fig.4 b), the conclusion can be given that the variety of injection pressure has little impact on the thickness of integral composites.

According to the discussion above, the optimal process parameters for manufacturing of PMI foam core sandwich integral composite by CIRTM are shown in Tab.1.

3.2 Property analysis

The integral composites specimen are manufactured using CIRTM method by the process parameters shown in Tab.1, contrastively, the multi-step composites specimen are fabricated by the method that fabricating the layers separately and subsequently bonding them together, the interlaminar shear test results are shown in Tab.2. Compared to the specimen fabricated by bonding step by step, the specimen fabricated by CIRTM have better interface strength, and the test values have lower coefficient of variance. The results show that co-curing process toughens the interface, and increases reliability of the multilayer composite structures.

Optical microscope is used to studied the microstructure of interface formed in co-curing course and secondarily bonding course respectively, the interface photos are shown as Fig.10 and Fig.11. It can be seen that the interface of each layer of multilayer structure by secondarily bonding have much porosities, since air bubble can be introduced in secondarily bonding course, and it is inevitable. But the interfaces of each layer of multilayer integral composites by CIRTM are excellent, few few porosities can be observed from optics photos, because the interface are formed in co-curing course. These are the main reasons cause the interlaminar shear test results.

Fig.1. CIRTM setup

Fig.2. Specimen sketch for interlaminar shear test

Fig.3. Interlaminar shear device

(a)With vacuum assisted

(b)Without vacuum assisted

Fig.4. Section photos of the specimen with and without vacuum assisted

(a) Carbon/epoxy layer side (b) Carbon/phenolic layer side

Fig.5 SEM photo of the specimen without vacuum assisted

(a) Carbon/epoxy layer side (b) Carbon/phenolic layer side

Fig.6. SEM photo of the specimen with vacuum assisted

(a)with fiber fraction of 38%

(b)with fiber fraction of 53.2%

Fig.7 Section photos of the specimen with fiber fraction of 38% and 53.2%

Fig.8 Section photo of the specimen with injection pressure of 0.3MPa

Fig.9 Section photo of the specimen with injection temperature of 90°C

Fig.10. Interface photo of composites by CIRTM

Fig.11. Interface photos of composites by secondarily bonding

Tab.1 Optimizal process parameters for manufacturing of PMI foam core sandwich integral composite by CIRTM

Process parameter	Fiber fraction	Injection pressure	Injection temperature	Vacuum assisted
Data	45.6%	0.1MPa	80°C	With

Tab.2. Interlaminar shear test results

Manufacturing process	Interfaces	Stress /MPa	Coefficient of variance/%
Secondarily bonding	Epoxy panel layer /Foam core layer	3.29	20.97
	Phenolic panel layer/Foam core layer	3.22	22.98
CIRTM	Epoxy panel layer /Foam core layer	3.82	7.07
	Phenolic panel layer/Foam core layer	3.36	9.52

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